

Tangled Crises and Temporalities: The 1958 Crisis in Lebanon

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This “Policy and Time” brief engages with the interplay between temporality, politics, and crises in Lebanon to better understand Lebanon’s historical and current dynamics. It focuses on the case of the 1958 crises in Lebanon to explore the nexus between these three elements, specifically focusing on how different crises and temporalities can intermingle, trigger, and build upon one another in often under-analyzed ways. The brief first provides a summary of the 1958 crisis in Lebanon, then provides conceptual foundations of the analysis related to periods of violent conflict, polycrisis, slow- and fast-burning crises, and political temporality. It then analyzes specific preceding and proceeding crises that merged into and emerged from 1958 in Lebanon, and includes recommendations for the inclusion of deeper awareness and engagement with crises and temporalities in Lebanon.

Summary of the 1958 Crisis in Lebanon

*“The events of 1958 mark a significant watershed in the political history of Lebanon”
(Khalaf, 2002, 142).*

The events that unfolded in 1958 in Lebanon are referred to as a crisis, conflict, civil war, insurrection, and/or revolution (Attié, 2020, 178; Khalaf, 2002, 21). There are additionally conflicting reports on the prominent causes of the crisis, with different sources prioritizing the role of the multiple dynamics at play (see Attié, 2004; Romero, 2012; Sorby, 2000 for examples).

Furthermore, and relevant for this analysis, there is not a commonly accepted start or end date to the crisis: analyses of this period in Lebanon sometimes include the Mandate period in Lebanon, the formation of Lebanon as an independent state, the outbreaks of violence in 1957, and/or continue until different dates into the fall of 1958. The amorphous nature of the situation being analyzed is an indication of the confusing and overlapping forces at play during this year in the country, which combined with the significance of the period for Lebanese political history, as noted in the Samir Khalaf quote above, provides a starting point for nuanced analysis of the alternative, conflicting, and overlapping elements. This is done through critical attention to the temporalities and interplay of the preceding and proceeding dynamics that together help to understand the shape this situation in Lebanon took in this specific time, as well as its ramifications for Lebanon since.

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What can be said about 1958 in Lebanon is that from the spring to the fall of 1958, the country saw a large-scale outbreak of violence between anti- and pro-government supporters, the arrival of a United Nations Observation Group, and the first combat mission of the United States military in the Middle East. The violence took various forms, including assassinations; protests, and repression of protests; strikes; targeted attacks on institutions and against security forces; and explosives in public areas (Qubain, 1961; Romero, 2012). The number of casualties during this period is stated to be around 3,000 (Khalaf, 2002, 143).

Conceptualizations of Temporality

In light of the above-stated complicated elements of the 1958 crisis in Lebanon, this brief aims to use a framework that helps to untangle and address individually and collectively several of the main forces at play through the use of existing conceptualizations of temporality in academic literature, specifically those on violent periods (McIntosh, 2016), those on how multiple crises can interact and compound one another (Tooze, 2022), and those on how temporality of politics meld across the past, present, and future (Little, 2022). First, as noted above, the terminology of what 1958 was in Lebanon varies, and this variety in terminology matters. What a violent event or period is called impacts what is covered, what dynamics are included, and its start and end; all of which affect the reading and analysis of the object in focus, as well as the temporal understanding of past, present, and future regarding the impact of this violence (McIntosh, 2016).

Second, the case of 1958 presents a convergence of several crises into one period, and therefore the term “polycrisis” bears relevance for its capturing of disparate shocks that “interact so that the whole is even more overwhelming than the sum of the parts” (Tooze, 2022). As will be addressed below, the 1958 crisis in Lebanon resulted from international, regional, and local crises, and this brief aims to use the case of 1958 in Lebanon to explore how these various crises compounded into several months of violence in the country. While this reading of the crisis in 1958 Lebanon has been noted elsewhere as having these national, regional, and international dynamics as causes (Attié, 2004; Qubain, 1961, Romero, 2012; Sorby, 2000), the temporal elements of these dynamics have not been appropriately cast as the focus of analysis. Therefore, in accordance with work in other geographic regions, this brief uses temporal analysis of crises as “fast-burning” and “slow-burning” to assist in thinking through how “crises can be differentiated by their perceived intensity and tempo:” fast-burning crises are “characterised by alarm and a demand for political action,” while slow-burning ones persist over time and there is often a lack of willingness or clarity as to how to political tackle these issues (Seabrook and Tsingou, 2019, 471-472).

Third, the conceptualization of this brief - as well as the wider work of this project - explores temporality as an approach to time that does not conceive of it as linear or separable into distinct categories of past, present, and future, but instead as an approach that engages with how these sections overlap and relate to one another. Specifically,

political temporality comes with a focus on lived experiences of time and on the fact that most political issues have important elements of lived experiences embedded within them, and therefore, have temporal elements that are contested and conflictual (Little, 2022).

Confessional Power Sharing and the Cold War: Slow-Burning Embers of Crises

One slow-burning crisis that surfaced in the 1958 crisis in Lebanon was the national demographic and confessional power-sharing system in Lebanon that was set into place with the establishment of Lebanon as a French mandate state in 1920. The geographic delineation of this state covered the territory of Greater Lebanon and included not only historically Muslim areas but also, as often-mentioned, inhabitants of 18 different religious sects. As a result, census-taking and power-sharing in the country have been politically charged along confessional lines. This dynamic was further locked in with the 1943 National Pact, an oral agreement that emerged from the preceding historical dynamics and concerns among Muslim and Christian leaders in the country. As both were concerned that the other would pull the country towards a regional or global power center that would threaten the other, the National Pact established that Lebanon would be independent from both Western and Arab alignments. Therefore, on the national level, this slow-burning power-and-demographic crisis resulting from Lebanon’s multi-confessional population was set in place in 1920, further codified in 1943, and has continued to brew in Lebanon, boiling over in 1958 (and periodically since; see below).

A second slow-burning crisis that erupted in the 1958 crisis in Lebanon came from global and regional dynamics related to the Cold War. While the Cold War began in 1947 and was a long-simmering global competition between the United States and the Soviet Union over global superpower dominance and competing ideologies, Cold War dynamics moved into the Middle East and locked into regional dynamics in the mid-1950s, notably with Gamal Abdel Nasser’s leadership of Egypt starting in 1954. Nasser’s growth in popularity as a pan-Arab leader with a socialist ideology began to stir and transform alignments among movements and states in the region, reaching a formative peak with the July 1956 Suez crisis. The Suez crisis was a decisive event that added fuel to the slow-burning crisis in Lebanon of Muslim groups in the country increasingly becoming inspired by and seeking alignment with Nasserism, along with other Middle Eastern countries, while the Lebanese government remained aligned with the West, namely France and the United Kingdom, during the crisis (Qubain, 1961, 48).

Eisenhower Doctrine and Parliamentary Elections: Embers Ignite and Crises Accelerate

In the year before the outbreak of the 1958 crisis in Lebanon, the above two crises coincided and both sped up in Lebanon, despite their divergent sources in internal,

regional, and international dynamics. This convergence was in part prompted by the United States Eisenhower Doctrine: a policy announced in January 1957 that countries in the Middle East could request economic or military assistance from the United States should they be threatened by armed aggression from any nation “controlled by international communism” (Little, 1996, 24). A few months later in March, Lebanese President Camille Chamoun openly and unreservedly endorsed the Eisenhower Doctrine, the only leader in the Middle East to do so. His overt support of the policy prompted other leaders and communities in Lebanon to condemn the act as a violation of the conditions established in the National Pact (Qubain, 1961, 46-47), thus escalating the internal Lebanese crisis of tensions around alliances to the East or West.

Tensions in Lebanon further increased in May 1957 over the Lebanese parliamentary elections due to issues regarding changed electoral laws, allegations of US influence over the elections, and accusations that Chamoun intended to modify the constitution to allow him to run for re-election, all of which triggered elements of the slow-burning crisis set into place with the country’s foundation (Everlane, 2018, 252; Qubain, 1961, 53-58; Romero, 2012, 569, 578). As a result, violence and unrest in the form of strikes, protests, attacks, and arrests periodically occurred throughout the country around the elections and continued into the following months (Khalaf, 2002, 108-111).

1958: Now Fast-Burning Crises Collide and Inflare

In the months leading up to the outbreak of the 1958 crisis in Lebanon, international, regional, and national dynamics in Lebanon continued to melt together and began flowing rapidly toward a crisis peak. On 1 February 1958, Syria and Egypt united as the United Arab Republic (UAR), a pan-Arab socialist unity led by Nasser in a regionally reconfiguring move that further splintered sentiments in Lebanon. President Chamoun initially refused to recognize the state while communities and movements within Lebanon were in support of the union and growing increasingly hostile to the President’s stance. Protests broke out throughout Lebanon and continued into April in several cities over flashpoints such as violence against and punishment of protesters, for the removal of the Lebanese flag, and for displaying visual signs of support for Nasser and the UAR (Qubain, 1961, 61-64; Romero, 2012, 569). The situation in the country “was like a powder keg” by the end of April as “violence and sabotage had become a daily occurrence” (Qubain, 1961, 67).

The pressure in the country exploded when Lebanese journalist and editor of *Al Telegraf* Nasib Al Matni, who was vocally critical of Chamoun and had been promoting stronger ties with the UAR, was assassinated in his office in Beirut on 8 May 1958. His assassination prompted the outbreak of strikes, further protests, and a new level of violence between pro- and anti-government groups in Beirut and Tripoli that divided the cities into conflict zones and spread to the other areas of Lebanon towards Syria (Qubain, 1961, 71-80). Radio statements from the UAR were seen to be inciting the unrest in

Lebanon and reports began emerging of anti-government groups in the Bekaa Valley receiving weapons from the UAR (Qubain, 1961, 80; Little, 1996, 39).

At the international level, in the early months of 1958 Chamoun’s government had been appealing for military support from the United States under the above-mentioned Eisenhower Doctrine, yet these requests had been consistently denied as the United States did not believe the situation in Lebanon warranted involvement (Traboulsi, 134-135). In light of this rejection, the Lebanese government filed a formal complaint to the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) on 22 May 1958 that accused the UAR of meddling in the nation's affairs, broadcasting propaganda and calls for revolt in Lebanon, and smuggling weapons (Attié, 2004, 215; Qubain, 1961, 89) The UNSC passed a resolution on 11 June 1958 recommending the formation of the United Nations Observation Group in Lebanon (UNOGIL) to monitor arms flows into the country from and interference in Lebanon from the UAR. The first of its members arrived in Lebanon on 12 June 1958, and by the beginning of July, the local tensions in Lebanon had ebbed, with President Chamoun ready to step down (Attié, 2020, 193-195; Little, 1996, 43).

However, at this moment another fast-burning crisis erupted at the regional level: a violent coup in Iraq on 14 July 1958 overthrew the United States-aligned Hashemite Kingdom of Iraq and established the Republic of Iraq. The coup stirred fears of Iraq and other countries in the region being ripped from Western alignment and towards socialist, pan-Arab alignment. The situation in Iraq therefore re-inflamed the crises in Lebanon; on the same day as the coup, President Chamoun asked the United States once again for military support, claiming that Lebanon would fall to the same fate as Iraq without support. This time, the United States acquiesced, and Marines arrived in Beirut the next day under “Operation Blue Bat” that sent 15,000 troops to Lebanon over the next few months (Traboulsi, 2012, 135-136).

On 31 July 1958, Fuad Shihab was elected President of Lebanon, and by the beginning of August, the fighting in Lebanon continued to die down (Qubain, 1961, 96). However, in September 1958 there was a resurgence in violence, sparked by the kidnapping and assumed killing of another journalist, Fuad Haddad, and resulting in several more weeks of violence until mid-October, at which point internal political compromises between warring groups once again decreased the level of violence (Khalaf, 2002, 137-142). The end of the calendar year brought with it the end of the 1958 crisis: American forces withdrew from Lebanon at the end of October 1958, the fighting in Lebanon was reported to have ceased by the beginning of November, and UNOGIL’s completed its mission and withdrew its members in the first half of December (Qubain, 1961, 109).

Dormant but not Extinguished: Lebanon’s Fast- and Slow-Burning Crises

The 1958 crisis in Lebanon can be seen not only as an event that resulted from the above varying crises across different temporalities and levels, but also as a seminal process that itself continued and increased forms of crises in Lebanon from 1958 onwards. It also

provides evidence for the benefit of greater attention to various temporalities of crises when analyzing political dynamics and events in Lebanon.

First, at the national level, the 1958 crisis unleashed “structural transformations” (Khalaf, 2002, 144) around politics, conflict, and violence that have “become embedded in Lebanon’s rather unusual legacy with civil strife in the country” (Khalaf, 2002, 146). These have re-emerged in the 1975-1990 civil war and other periods of violence in the country since. Perhaps most notable is the fact that the 1958 crisis had “no victor, no vanquished” and was “resolved” without “fundamental changes” to the country, which “became the formula for peace in Lebanon” after subsequent periods of violence until the present day (Sorby, 2002, 109, see also Khalaf, 2002, 51-52). Other examples of patterns set in 1958 that have continued in periods of crisis since include the political use of radio and other forms of media (Khazaal, 2020; Qubain, 1961, 80), the armed division of cities and regions into controlled areas (Khalaf, 2002, 246-248; Qubain, 1961, 73-80), and how violence takes on a life of its own once started (Khalaf, 2002, 49-50). These dynamics serve as evidence of how past crises can produce embers of new crises that smolder and reignite over time in the country.

Second, also nationally, the crisis in 1958 can be seen as an example of how new crises can build upon and entrench previous ones. As noted, both the 1958 crisis and the 1975-1990 civil war did not fundamentally change the internal power-sharing dynamics in the country. Therefore, the confessional system in Lebanon can be seen as a persistent slow-burning crisis that ignited in the 1958 crisis and the later fifteen-year-long civil war, and has since spread to ignite other political and social crises in the country until today, including the 2019 financial collapse and revolution and the 2020 Beirut port explosion. This case shows that the relationship between fast- and slow-burning crises in Lebanon can be intertwined yet unconnected: just because the former de-escalates does not mean that the latter has been extinguished.

Third, at the regional level, as fast- and slow-burning crises from the wider Middle East spilled over and impacted the 1958 crisis, so they have continued to do so in Lebanon. This can be seen in the ways that regional dynamics became heavily involved in the 1975-1990 civil war, and in how these same (and new) regional dynamics have continued to implicate Lebanon as a country until today. Notable examples of the regional impacts on Lebanon are the (real and perceived) impacts related to the influx of Palestinian refugees in 1948 and their continual presence; those related to competition and tensions between regional actors such as Iran, Syria, and Israel; and those related to internal national developments, such as the Syrian revolution and subsequent civil war that then spilled over into Lebanon. Analysis of Lebanon needs to continue to be sensitive to how regional crises and their temporalities can spread to and involve Lebanon as a “battleground” to have compounding impacts on both the country and the region.

Last, the 1958 crises in Lebanon sparked patterns of involvement from the international level that need to be acknowledged. One such display of this pattern is the arrival and long-lasting presence of the United Nations in the country: in addition to the UN’s 1958

mission, this involvement has continued with the 1978 establishment of the United Nations Interim Force in Lebanon that remains in the south of the country until today. Additionally, the US interference in Lebanon in 1958 kicked off a long-lasting and convoluted legacy of military actions. The US decision to militarily intervene in Lebanon in 1958 set the scene for the return of its military to Beirut in 1982 during the civil war as part of a multinational peacekeeping force; for the United States’ repeated and long-lasting military engagements in other Middle Eastern countries, such as Iraq; and for its overall decision-making process to become militarily embroiled in other countries globally, such as Vietnam (Gendzier, 2006; Karam, 2020, 48; Little, 1996). Therefore, international involvement in crises in Lebanon has set into place patterns and practices that have impacted not only Lebanon, but also the intervening entities themselves, as well as other countries targeted for similar interventions.

In conclusion, analyzing the 1958 crisis in Lebanon through an approach that prioritizes a focus on multiple layers of analysis and temporalities allows for tracing how crises interact whilst accounting for their ebbs and flows of intensity through time. This approach bears use specifically for Lebanon as it untangles slow- and fast-burning political crises that can lay dormant and reignite in the country, sometimes with seemingly minor triggers from international, regional, or local developments. Analysis, policy, and practice in Lebanon all need greater awareness of and sensitivity to the overlapping and interacting temporal dynamics of multiple crises in Lebanon to better understand, respond to, and predict crises in Lebanon.

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